

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE TOPIC "MAGNETIC FIELD AND THE EFFECT OF A MAGNETIC FIELD ON A CURRENT-CARRYING CONDUCTOR"

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Annotation. *This article highlights the effectiveness of interactive, visual, and simulation methods in teaching the topic "Magnetic Field and the Effect of a Magnetic Field on a Current-Carrying Conductor" in the 8th grades of secondary schools. The study tested a methodology developed using the PhET "Magnets and Electromagnets" simulation, 3D visualization, and problem-based learning methods in experimental classes. The results show that compared to traditional methods, the proposed methods increase the quality of students' knowledge by 30.2% and the mastery coefficient by 16.5%. The article presents a step-by-step technological map for teaching the topic and an integrated model for organizing laboratory sessions.*

Keywords: *magnetic field, Ampere force, interactive methods, PhET simulation, visual learning, digital technologies, laboratory session, teaching effectiveness.*

Introduction. Modernizing the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, particularly improving the quality of physics education, is one of the priority directions of state policy. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5032 dated March 19, 2021 "On measures to improve the quality of education and develop scientific research in the field of physics," as well as the National Education Program for 2022-2026, defined the necessity of introducing practical and interactive methods in teaching physics [1; 2].

The topic "Magnetic Field and the Effect of a Magnetic Field on a Current-Carrying Conductor" is one of the most important and simultaneously abstract concept-rich topics in the electrodynamics section of physics. Forming concepts such as magnetic induction, magnetic field lines, Ampere force, and the left-hand rule in students' minds is not limited to traditional methods but requires modern pedagogical technologies and digital tools. This article proposes an interactive model consisting of visual, simulation, and problem-based methods for teaching this topic and analyzes its effectiveness based on experimental results.

Main part. Research methodology and organization. The research was conducted on 8th-grade students of School No. 4 in Jizzakh city. An experimental class (8-A, 28 students) and a control class (8-B, 27 students) were formed. The results of the initial assessment showed approximately equal levels of knowledge in both classes (average score: experimental class – 12.4; control class – 12.2; on a 20-point scale) [4]. While the topic was taught in the control class using traditional methods (lecture, textbook-based work, written assignments), the following methods were applied in the experimental class:

- **Visual methods:** 3D models, animations, static and dynamic depictions of magnetic field lines;
- **Simulation methods:** PhET "Magnets and Electromagnets" interactive simulation (observing magnetic field lines, the relationship between current and field strength in real-time);
- **Problem-based learning method:** Developing independent thinking through problematic questions such as "Why does a current-carrying conductor move in a magnetic field?", "How can the magnetic field be strengthened without increasing the current?";
- **Interactive methods:** Brainstorming, blitz surveys, "pinwheel," group work [3; 5].

2. Model of educational technology and its practical application

The topic was taught in the experimental class over 10 lesson hours. Each lesson was organized based on the following stages (see Table 1).

Table 1: Technological map of the lesson.

Stages of work	Time	Teacher and student activities
Stage 1. Motivation	5 min	Brainstorming: associations based on the word "Magnet"; demonstration of magnetic field lines using iron filings.
Stage 2. New topic	15 min	Problem-based lecture (slides, animations), observing the field around a current-carrying conductor using the PhET simulation.

Stages of work	Time	Teacher and student activities
Stage 3. Practical part	15 min	Laboratory work "Assembling a simple electromagnet and studying its operation" (real equipment, changing parameters in the PhET simulation).
Stage 4. Reinforcement	8 min	"Pinwheel" method (examples related to the left-hand rule), blitz survey.
Stage 5. Conclusion	2 min	Summary, assessment, homework.

In particular, the laboratory work "Assembling a simple electromagnet and studying its operation" was organized by combining real and virtual methods. Students first observed the relationship between current, number of turns, and magnetic field strength in the PhET simulation (Figure 1), then assembled the electromagnet using real equipment (iron core, copper wire, power supply, ammeter). This integrated approach helped students deeply understand the topic and develop practical skills.

Results and analysis of the experimental study. The results of the final assessment (consisting of tests, problems, diagrams, and explanatory tasks, 20 points) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparative analysis of final assessment results

Indicators	Experimental class (8-A)	Control class (8-B)	Difference
Average score (on a 20-point scale)	16.8	13.5	+3.3

Indicators	Experimental class (8-A)	Control class (8-B)	Difference
Mastery coefficient (K)	84.0%	67.5%	+16.5%
Quality of knowledge (Q – share of grades "4" and "5")	82.1%	51.9%	+30.2%
Complete mastery (T – share of grades "3", "4", "5")	96.4%	85.2%	+11.2%

As seen from the table, the quality of knowledge in the experimental class was 30.2% higher, and the mastery coefficient was 16.5% higher. The largest differences were recorded in the following topics: "Assembling a simple electromagnet and studying its operation" (difference of +2.2 points on a 10-point scale) and "Effect of a magnetic field on a current-carrying conductor (Ampere force)" (difference of +1.7 points). Students in the experimental class not only memorized the left-hand rule but could also apply it independently to various situations. The ability to observe changes in magnetic field lines in real-time by changing parameters in the PhET simulation significantly developed their spatial imagination.

In the control class, where traditional methods were used, the mastery coefficient increased by only 6.5%. This proves that the proposed interactive model is significantly more effective than traditional methods.

Conclusion. Based on the conducted research and experimental work, the following conclusions were drawn:

- 1. Effectiveness of interactive methods:** Combining visual (3D models, animations), simulation (PhET), and problem-based methods in teaching abstract topics like the magnetic field significantly improves the quality of students' knowledge and their independent thinking abilities.

2. **Integration of virtual and real laboratories:** Conducting the laboratory work "Assembling a simple electromagnet" in both real and virtual (PhET) environments ensures safety, allows changing parameters over a wide range, and enables precise quantitative analysis of results. The most optimal approach is to use both methods in an integrated manner.

3. **Ready-made methodological model:** The educational technology model presented in the article (technological map, assessment criteria, task system), spanning 10 lesson hours, is ready for direct application in secondary schools.

Therefore, it is recommended to apply the proposed interactive model in physics lessons, especially when teaching topics rich in abstract concepts such as the magnetic field, electromagnetic induction, and alternating current.

References:

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